

UDC: 42.43. (07)

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Based on the review of ASFLI Ph.D. A.L.Mamatkulov

READING STRATEGIES UNDER THE ESP APPROACH

Annotation

This article discusses how to implement reading under the parameters of ESP (English for Specific Purposes) through the communicative approach. ESP texts must be linked to student specific specialization, which acquire specific vocabulary and information as well as improving in the use of English as a foreign language.

Key words: Communicative approach, specific reading, reading strategies, proficiency.

СТРАТЕГИИ ЧТЕНИЯ В СООТВЕТСТВИИ С ПОДХОДОМ ESP

Аннотация

В этой статье обсуждается, как реализовать чтение по параметрам ESP (English for Specific Purposes) посредством коммуникативного подхода. Тексты ESP должны быть связаны с конкретной специализацией учащихся, которые приобретают определенный словарный запас и информацию, а также улучшают использование английского языка как иностранного.

Ключевые слова: Коммуникативный подход, специфическое чтение, стратегии чтения, мастерство.

ESP YONDASHISHI BO'YICHA O'QISH STRATEGIYASI

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada kommunikativ yondashuv orqali ESP (Maxsus maqsadlar uchun ingliz tili) parametrlari ostida o'qishni qanday amalga oshirish mumkinligi muhokama qilinadi. ESP matnlari talabalarining maxsus ixtisosligi bilan bog'langan bo'lishi kerak, ular o'ziga xos lug'at va ma'lumotlarni oladi, shuningdek, ingliz tilidan chet tili sifatida foydalanishni yaxshilaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: Kommunikativ yondashuv, maxsus o'qish, o'qish strategiyalari, malaka.

The English learning processes have been changing according to students' needs; consequently ESP is the result of this change. It was born because advanced and adult learners felt the need to acquire knowledge of their own fields of study taking into account that English has been an important language in disciplines such as engineering, architecture, computer science, health, precision instrument, environment protection, accounting, and economics, among others.

ESP could be described as a specific branch of English focused to train students in specific areas, or as Laurence Anthony (1997:1) points out: "English can be used in academic studies or the teaching of English for vocation or professional purposes", which represents the students' needs.

On another hand, Gatehouse, K. (2001:2) identifies three aspects that influenced the origin and growth of ESP: "the demand of a brave new world, a revolution in linguistics and focus on the learning." Which show the expansion of science and technology at United States and its control over the world. Teaching English evolved in the way to look for new possibilities; Hutchinson, T., Walters, A., et al. point out that a meaningful discovery was in the ways that spoken and written English vary according to the particular context in which it is used. This assumption permits us to understand the origin of ESP as the necessity of learners to explore specific contexts, motivated by different needs and interests.

Finally, specialists in teaching, use an ESP approach as base in their syllabus, taking into account the learners' needs or their reasons for learning and their own personal specialized knowledge, using English for real communication. At the same time, it is necessary to have in mind the types of ESP in order to analyze the most appropriated according to the situation and context of students, which is point out in Carver, D.'s (1983) classification:

English as a restricted language
English for Academic and Occupational Purposes
English with specific topics
English as a Restricted Language.

It means that teachers have to take care to present students just the necessary language patterns needed for the topic students are going to work; for example if they are going to work about family members and relationships; the vocabulary and expressions have to be totally related with the topic. Thus, the language is restricted focuses to the topic.

English for Academic and Occupational Purposes. It was created as a need for people who work; they are also identified:

English for Academic Purposes (EAP) and English for Occupational Purposes (EOP). Hutchinson & Waters et al, (1987), proposed three branches: call
a) English for Science and Technology (EST).
b) English for Business and Economics (EBE).
c) English for Social Studies (ESS).

As we can see, this classification is done by the conditions given in the workplace in the way to have more tools for education. About it, Hutchinson, T., & Waters, A. et al. (1987) say that an effective syllabus must attempt to overcome the lacks of the educational system under which they are operating.

English with Specific Topics. It makes emphasis in the purpose of particular topics and is specially applied for postgraduate reading studies, Gatehouse, K. et al, (2001: 4) manifests: "This type of ESP is uniquely concerned with anticipated future English needs, for example, scientists requiring English for postgraduate reading studies, attending conferences or working in foreign institutions". Therefore, this kind of language is prepared in the way to be applied in a

functional way to people who need it for their future as professional form example Minci I. H., Demirel, O. et al (1999: 82) from Kinkale University and Hacettepe University developed an ESP reading curriculum and one of their goals was: “to choose or prepare a functional and practical. ESP reading material for the students in where, they will have the opportunity to gain both general reading skills and the knowledge of the English terminology related to Mathematics, Physics and Chemistry”. This study was developed with architecture and engineering students, who gained acquisition of general and specific knowledge items in mathematics and English language.

The communicative approach is based on the idea that learning language successfully comes through having to communicate real meaning. When learners are involved in real communication, their natural strategies for language acquisition will be used, and this will allow them to learn to use the language. Hutchinson and Waters et al. (1987: 5) says, “ESP is an approach to language teaching in which all decisions as to content and method are based on the learner’s reason for learning”.

Communicative language teaching makes use of real-life situations integrated to the need of communication. The teacher sets up situations that students are likely to encounter in real life, creates the appropriate environment in order to stimulate tasks that permit students to be the protagonists of their own learning, with activities such as conferences, preparation of papers, reading, note taking and writing. Berns (1984:10) comments: “The real-life simulations change daily. Students’ motivation to learn comes from their desire to communicate in meaningful ways about meaningful topics.” Of course, the teacher can also take into account the disciplines of students to guide the activities.

Hart, G. Proposes some basic principles for the language learning approach in use today: Teachers’ Basic Principles

- A teacher’s main role is a facilitator and monitor rather than leading the class.

In other words, “the guide by the side” and; in this point Jin, L., Singh, M., Li,

L. (2005:7) manifest according to their own research experience: “The teachers’ task in class is to help students understand the discourse structure of what they were reading. This is an efficient way to understand the reading of materials and get the main ideas”

- Lessons are built round situations/functions practical and authentic in the real world e.g. asking for information, complaining, apologizing, job interviews, telephoning, etc.

- Activities set by the teacher have relevance and purpose to real life situations – students can see the direct benefit of learning.

- Authentic listening and reading texts are used more often, rather than artificial texts simply produced to feature the target language.

- Use of songs and games are encouraged and provide a natural environment to promote language and enhance correct pronunciation.

- Feedback and correction are usually given by the teacher after tasks.

Additionally, while reading there are some processes the teacher has to enhance such as the top-down and bottom-up which occur at the same time. In bottom-up processing, learners solve problems relevant to language knowledge themselves, in this point, Murcia and Olshtain (2000:7) say: “Teachers gradually introduce knowledge about cohesive devices and reading strategies which influence their reading habits.” In top down students get information from reading

based on their previous knowledge of their daily life or from their schemata.

Learners’ Basic Principles:

- Learners are often more motivated if they have the possibility to communicate through different lessons or themes.

- Learners practice the target language a number of times according to their own capacities and needs.

- Language is built individually by students based on their own work experience.

- Learners interact with each other in pairs or groups.

In the accuracy stage, learners are corrected at the end of an activity to avoid the interruption of their thought process.

The material is important aspect. It should take into account during developing ESP reading under the parameters of a communicative approach because it is the teachers’ main resource; in this way, before starting a project like this, it is necessary to make a good collection of materials; it could be composed by specialized books, articles, and web side pages among others.

Jones, G. (1990: 89) proposes: “The only real solution is that a resource bank of materials has to be available to all ESP instructions”. However there is the possibility that teachers create their own materials, according to their experience and as part of their growing as teachers.

Another important aspect is that through communicative approach, teachers help students to develop autonomy, they frequently practice speaking in the classroom through communicative exercises, but previously practice the other abilities (listening, reading and writing). In order to get the input and reorganize his own thinking and knowledge, Larsen-Freeman (1986:22) argues: “Because of the increased responsibility to participate, students may gain confidence in using the target language in general. Students are more responsible managing their own learning.” It makes of this approach, a good option to work with students of all levels and subjects; at the same time Carver, D. states: “The learners must have a certain degree of freedom to decide when, what, and how they will study. Also there must be a systematic attempt by teachers to teach the learners how to learn by teaching them about learning strategies.” Nowadays it is necessary to motivate students to work for their own in the way to acquire information through new technologies, because with means of communication as the Internet they have all in their hands to access information according to their needs.

Reading is taken under the parameters of ESP because this is our field of study, so authors such as Anthony, L., et al. (1997: 5) says “The mayor quantity of information that a person receives is through reading, which is useful to improve the vocabulary and the rhetoric forms used in people’s profession. Nowadays, reading has been the base of the curricula of ESP” The goal of reading is to get information you need for specific or personal purposes, thus, reading comprehension evolves understanding and decoding a text or constructing through a process.

Additionally, reading in ESP, following the parameters of the communicative approach. Reading under the ESP Approach requires the usual - pre-reading, while- reading and post-reading – activities:

- * Pre-reading activities prepare students to do an efficient reading, it is related to students’ background, which facilitates comprehension. Lebauer (1998:5) points out: “Pre-reading activities can lighten students’ cognitive burden while reading because prior discussions will have been incorporated.” Therefore, teachers have to enhance pre-reading activities as a useful habit in students to do an efficient reading.

If students are conscious about what they are going to read, or what do they want to know after reading; they are going to be able to guide themselves along reading, this processes permit them to focus their attention in the purpose of reading; Brown considers the following types of reading skills.

Skimming: fast reading to get the main idea.

Scanning: fast reading to get specific information.

Extensive reading: Reading longer texts, often for pleasure with emphasis on overall meaning.

Intensive reading: Reading short texts for detailed information.

The previous skills are useful, especially for students who are studying a foreign language because they feel the urge to look up every word, they don't understand and to pinpoint on every structural aspects they see unfamiliar. In this way, they can have a global view of the text, which facilitates their process of understanding, and have priority of the information.

Teachers' experience in reading processes show that before reading there is a short period of time which has to be used in good way in order take advantage of meaningful activities encouraging students to read.

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